

Design, analysis and construction of a bending-active tensile hybrid structure

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Abstract

This paper examines the design, simulation and construction of a bending-active tensile hybrid structure, designed as cantilevered roof, part of the ‘ITECH Research Demonstrator 2017-18’, a collaborative project between ITKE and ICD. The hybrid structure, which will be referred to as ‘pringle’ for the continuation of this paper, investigates the complex reciprocal interaction between bending and torsion in a plate and pure tension in two surface elements, their interdependence in the simulation process and advantage during construction.

Keywords: form-finding, hybrid structure, bending-active, composites, membrane structures

1. Introduction

The so-called ‘pringle’ was part of the latest collaboration (ITECH Research Demonstrator 2017-18) between the Institute of Building Structures and Structural design (ITKE) and the Institute for Computational Design and Construction (ICD), both part of the University of Stuttgart. The project, that was an outcome of the design-and-build studio of the ITECH Masters Programme, was built on the Stadtmitte Campus of the University in October 2018. The ‘pringle’ was the static part of the adaptable bending-active structure and was designed as a lightweight spatial roof. The structure itself was a local bending-active tensile hybrid, which was self-stressed-equilibrated, as defined by Slabbinck *et al.* [1] and thus resolves the forces, to keep the bending-active plate in bending and torsion, within the system itself.

Figure 1: (From left to right) Finished pringle; and ‘ITECH Research Demonstrator 2017-18’ [Photograph by Burggraf / Reichert]

2. Background and context

The aesthetic and material qualities of bending-active tensile hybrid structures has intrigued architects and engineers over the past decades. These structures refer to coupled systems of tensile form- and bending-active components in which stiffness was gained through reciprocal stress dependency and elastic deformations of parental systems [2]. Concrete, prestress in membranes was introduced through the elastic deformation of bending-active components whose shape was in turn controlled by the deformation of membranes. Such hybrid constructions commonly refer to structures that integrate slender elastic beams with prestressed membranes, but the dimensionality of the bending-active components may not be limited to linear elements as described in La Magna [3]. The integration of elastic bent elements within prestressed membranes permits to design a self-tensioned solution. Moreover, the great advantage is that complex free-form geometries can be created from simple and planar components. However, the task of designing such hybrid constructs was not trivial due to the unpredictability of their geometry, and requires a shape optimization process called form-finding.

3. Integrative design concept

The local hybrid structure (pringle) was designed to fit a primary structure (ITECH Research Demonstrator 2017-18) that was conceived from a complex aggregation of elastically bent CFRP (carbon fiber reinforced polymers) plates. The primary structure was shaped from five different types of plate morphologies and composed of two self-equilibrated assemblies for defining a space with adaptable levels of enclosure. The completed ‘pringle’ has a span of approx. 4.2 m, a width of 3 m and a height of 1 m. The magnitude of prestress was related to the geometry and scale of the membranes and was preferred to be between 0.2 and 1 kN/m. This structure was designed as a doubly-curved element composed of an initially straight GFRP (glass fiber reinforced polymer) plate with slim constant rectangular cross-section that was first bent into a closed ring and then twisted for coupling two structural PTFE-GF (polytetrafluoroethylene coated glass fiber) membranes to the corresponding upper and lower edges of the plate. In doing so, both membranes didn’t require to be mechanically prestressed with edge cables, which was a desirable condition for facilitating the erection process, and enabled the use of GF-continuity for the whole structure including the connections. When twisting the closed ring, a state of over-torsion needs to be created in order to connect the edges of both membranes to a set of fixed points that were uniformly distributed along the ring. Consequently, the bending and torsion of the plate was used as a mechanism to prestress the membranes during construction, to avoid loss of prestress after a certain timeframe, to generate structural stiffness, and to fit the overall designed shape of the primary structure. The final doubly-curved geometry of the structure was then solely held in shape by the prestress of both membranes, which avoids the plate deforming back to a ring-shape. This condition permits to design a self-stressed-equilibrated system in which the stresses introduced on the membranes through the elastic deformation of the plate were internally solved with null reaction forces acting on the primary structure. The amount and direction of torsion and bending induced on the plate was in direct relation with the required curvature and prestress to withstand external loading and to have a rigid overall equilibrium shape. This was because the amount of double curvature induced on membranes by the elastic deformation of the plate constituted the fundamental mechanism to withstand external loads since their stiffness for bending and compression was almost neglectable. Both membranes fall into the typology of “barrel vaults” as their edges are continuously clamped. The top membrane has the main prestress direction in the sagging curvature direction and the bottom membrane in the hogging curvature direction, wherefore the upper and lower membrane can take the selected forces caused by downward and uplift wind. In addition to its structural capabilities, the geometry was conceptually designed to address functional and aesthetical criteria. The asymmetric prestress direction in both membranes generated an elliptical shape in top view and a curved shape in both lateral views, which creates multiple spatial experiences from different viewpoints.

4. Material design and testing

Quadraxial glass fiber fabric (EQX 1200, 1210 g/m²) in combination with an epoxy was used to fabricate the GFRP loop. The epoxy resin RIMR 135 (EPIKOTE Resin MGS RIMR 135) was chosen, as this forms a comparably flexible thermoset with an elongation at break of 8-12 % [4]. With the curing agent RIMR 1366 (EPIKURE Curing Agent MGS RIMH 1366) the resin has a long pot life of 210 minutes and cures at room temperature within 24 hours [4]. In combination with a low viscosity these properties make it especially suitable for large-scale bending-active structures fabricated in a manual process and the later material connection of the membrane to the GFRP. The used membrane was a typical woven glass fiber fabric coated with PTFE to ensure material consistency and show the potential of a continuous material transition from a stiff plate to membrane. The advantages here of using a PTFE-coated glass fiber fabric was a relatively low level of creep, which could avoid re-tensioning, having a non-sticky surface to avoid dirt build-up, and being a relative stiff material, which reduces the deflections of the membrane under external loading [5]. For connection of the membrane to the plate, a 12.5 cm wide band of uncoated glass fiber was welded to the coated fabric (7234 AF, KASTILO). The PTFE shows brownish color that changes to white under the influence of UV light after several weeks.

Even though the membrane material has a non-linear biaxial stress-strain behavior, a uniaxial tensile test was conducted to get initial results. To measure potential creep of the membrane at the given load level, a cyclic load test of 50 mm wide membrane stripes was conducted. In four cycles the load was varied from an estimated prestress state (25 N; 0.5 kN/m) to a maximum load possibly occurring during its life-time of 500 N (10 kN/m), which for every cycle was applied three times in a row (testing speed: 10 mm/min, Zwick/ROELL universal testing machine, clamping length: 200 mm, distance displacement sensors: 100 mm, pre-force: 5 N). Between the cycles, the load was held at the estimated prestress of the membrane for one hour. The mean strain remaining at prestress level after the four load cycles was 2.6 ± 0.1 %. For the three specimen tested no increase in the maximum membrane strain was measured over the number of cycles. The mean strain of all cycles at 500 N for all three samples was 4.4 ± 0.1 %.

Figure 2: Cyclic load-test of the PTFE coated glass fiber membrane

In order to test the material connection between the GFRP and the membrane close to the later occurring loads, a GFRP plate in the estimated thickness of the later GFRP ring (approx. 10 mm) was fabricated and the edges sanded to form a smooth edge with a constant radius. The membrane with the weld-connected uncoated glass fiber fabric was then laminated to it. Beforehand the GFRP plate surface was sanded and cleaned using isopropanol. The membrane was positioned in such a way that the laminated connection ends 20 mm before the GFRP plate edge to avoid brittle resined fibers in that region and ensure that the flexible membrane curves around the rounded plate edge in order to avoid fiber breakage. After letting the resin cure for 24 hours at room temperature, to the free end of the coated membrane a load of 250 N was applied perpendicular to the GFRP plate orientation, following the later direction of prestress and loading. Due to the lack of sample material, no test series determining the exact failure load with an appropriate specimen number was possible to conduct. However, in the above described prototype test, the load applied to the 50 mm wide sample was 10 times higher than the expected

membrane prestress of 0.5 kN/m. After 7 days in this position, placed in a workshop environment including mild vibrations and moderate wind loads, no damage was visible at the specimen. Also a small mockup with a diameter of 1.8 m was built to learn how the material interacts with the geometry.

The Young's modulus of the GFRP was measured by a three-point bending test according to DIN EN ISO 14125. In a conservative approach, a fiber orientation in the outermost fiber layer perpendicular to the bending direction of the tested plate was chosen to get the lowest possibly occurring stiffness and strength used for the subsequent calculations. For the test, the distance of supports was 400 mm, the testing speed 5 mm/min and a sample width and thickness of 150 mm and 15 mm respectively. For the GFRP a Young's modulus of 13.5 ± 0.1 GPa and a strength of 330 ± 2 MPa were measured. In addition, prototypes of the integrated connection's threads were tested for the calculated maximum bending moments and were able to bear them.

5. Structural design methodology

Due to the strong reciprocal interaction between both types of structural elements, i.e. the bending-active plate and the two membranes, the structural behavior of the pringle was highly complex and required a simultaneous iterative nonlinear form-finding process. This interaction together with the observed material property variations, membrane orientation, prestress direction, and custom bond connections have a great influence on the simulation results and the overall behavior of the structure. The resulting 3D shape was developed through a multistep computational workflow in which each construction step was parametrically modeled in CAD software Rhinoceros-Grasshopper (Rhinoceros 3D© - Grasshopper©), and numerically form-found and analyzed with the commercial Finite Element Modeling (FEM) software Sofistik (SOFiSTiK AG©). Design iterations (e.g. form-finding and structural-mechanical analysis) needed to be rapidly as it was intertwined with the parallel design of the primary structure. Easy bidirectional transfer of data between Grasshopper and Sofistik were achieved by using an in-house ITKE-plugin so that results from one software could be used in the other to generate the next step in the analysis and modeling process. Because of this parametric workflow there was a smooth collaboration between the different expert student teams and allowed working on different aspects and scales of the structure. Simulation of the bending-active plates in FEM software, utilizes third-order-theory calculations, where for every iteration step, a new equilibrium was calculated on the actual updated deformed shape. "*The Elastic Cable Approach*" [2] was applied to simulate controlled and gradually the large elastic deformations. Similar use of the geometrical non-linear FE analysis was used for simulating the tensile elements, which was defined as a continuum analysis [5].

The bending of the initially straight 12-meter-long plate (using plane elements) into a circular ring was modeled in by applying a bending moment at both ends. The bending stresses were compared with straightforward hand calculations. In a second step, torsion was applied to obtain the desired elliptical shape. Torsion of the plate was used as a design driver, described in paragraph 3, and led also to the advantage of gaining geometrical stiffness [6]. The thickness of the plate was defined by utilizing it to 50 % of the maximum tensile and shear strength, and to 60 % in the over-torsion state during construction, while keeping the normal forces in the modeling cables and the reaction forces in the supports in an acceptable limit.

The mesh of the membrane was generated in Grasshopper, based on form-found geometry of the GFRP plate in FEM. This implied working on a polygonal boundary with a pre-defined number of fixed vertices; therefore, the mesh was generated through a relaxation technique in order to match this predefined discretization of the boundary. To do this, an initial planar quad mesh was constructed with the same number of naked vertices than those of the pre-given discrete boundary. By mapping in a sorted sequence the corresponding vertices on both discrete geometries, the naked boundary of the planar quad mesh was pulled towards the geometry of the pre-given boundary. Then, the internal edges of the quad-mesh were relaxed as a cable-net system to create a structured quad mesh fitting the elliptical doubly

curved geometry of the boundary. This input of the mesh in Sofistik was defined as a three-dimensional initial system, and was restricted by hinge supports all along the boundary. The initial form-finding step of the simulation was using a temporary reduced stiffness, so the strains don't lead to a stress modification [7]. Afterwards, a second calculation was done where the stiffness was set to its normal stiffness. To keep the required elliptical shape, an asymmetric prestress was needed, the applied prestress in the main direction was 0.5 kN/m (warp), and 0.2 kN/m in the secondary direction (weft). The additional local stiffening of the cutting pattern seams was not taken into consideration.

To assure that the correct 3D-geometry of the plate was used for the precise cutting pattern, the plate was scanned with a panorama laser scanner (Faro Focus3D 120). Because of the elastic property-form relationship differences between the achieved and initial simulated configuration of the structural system occurred. The membrane simulation was remodeled based on the measured data to include any effects of deviations. The two types of structural elements were brought together to form-find the structure as a whole. The spring-back effect of the plate was brought in relation with the stress values of the membrane. These results were used for the design iterations of the primary structure and the load analysis of the pringle itself. The load analysis under external loading uses the following available European Standards: "Eurocode for wind actions" (BS EN 1991-1-4:2005) and "Temporary structures – Tents – Safety" (BS EN 13782:2005). The structure was designed to be erected for a few months during summer and therefore no snow load was considered. The aim of the membrane analysis was to control the deflections so that no ponding or wrinkling of the membrane occurs, neither collision with other structural elements. The wind analysis was conducted on two separate levels. First, a uniform uplifting wind load of 1 kN/m² perpendicular to the lower membrane surface was applied, and similar a downward wind loading on the top membrane. Second, a reduced wind load according to the EC-zones with sucking and pushing wind force was applied to assess the local characteristic values where the sign changes. As the hybrid simulation was complex, the anisotropic prestress solutions were unknown as described by Gosling *et al.* [5], the material properties were less well defined and no wind tunnel testing for this complex form was available, the simulation and stress asses required significant engineering deliberation. After the form-finding of the membrane, the geometry was exported to CAD as part of the parametric workflow, where the geodesic lines were generated. The 3D cutting areas were then loaded back into Sofistik for developing into a 2D plane in respect of (de)compensation, creep and prestress. The compensation factor was experimentally defined, cf. paragraph 4, while a reduced factor was used in the weft direction. The most outer elements of the pattern were decompensated as it was nearly impossible to tangentially stress them.

Figure 3: Overview structural design methodology

6. Fabrication

A 12 m long flat plate with a thickness of 11 mm and width of 35 cm was produced in a hand-lamination process from 12 layers of the quadraxial glass fiber fabric, leaving 50 cm of the glass fiber fabric at both sides unimpregnated. A vacuum of 100 mbar was applied to get rid of excess resin. In a second step, the

plate was bent into a circle, the two edges fixed and the overlapping unresined glass textiles were fitted together with ply-wise varying location and angle of the meeting edges and impregnated with the same process as for the rest of the plate. After curing and loosening of all external fixations a perfectly circular round glass fiber ring was achieved. Composite screws were embedded for construction purpose and to later connect to the primary structure.

Figure 4: Overview plate fabrication process

The cutting pattern of the top membrane existed out of 12 pieces, and the bottom one of 8. The seam line was aligned with the warp direction of the fabric, the direction of the main prestress and the main principles curvatures. In consequence both membranes are relative to each other oppositely oriented. Onto the boundary of the PTFE-GF membrane, a piece of uncoated GF was attached and as well PTFE-GF-flaps (two per membrane strip), for construction purposes. The membrane was welded together with a high frequency welding machine, due to the complexity of the already 3D formed membrane, the additional flaps and GF-strip were welded by hand.

7. Construction

To achieve the target geometry of the composite structural elements, different construction phases and stress states have to be passed through. The process of connecting the membrane to the plate-ring leads to the intended shape changes of both load-bearing elements.

In the first step the ring with circular shape was put into a custom made jig to twist it into an elliptical shape (a first time for surveying and a second time for the construction several weeks later). Due to an inclination change of two lever arms of the jig, the ring was torsioned and bent (step 1) to later prestress the first layer of membrane through a spring back effect. The membrane was put upon the edge of the elliptically bent ring (step 2). To establish the planned pretension situation, temporary flaps were pulled piecewise outwards beyond the ring edge with tension belts against composite screws or hooks on the lower ring edge. The ends of the membrane flaps were reinforced by clamping in between a pair of CFRP blocks, which were bolted together and provided a whole to attach a tension strap. The ends of the fabric in the secondary prestress direction were pulled with a cable winch in the first round of tensioning. Every tension strap was gradually tensioned in a clockwise fashion until the membrane established its targeted prestress state. As it was not possible to conduct a biaxial test of the material, the elongation of the membrane was observed during installation, and the amount of tensioning was modified to the local status. In the next step (step 3), the membrane was adhesively connected (laminated) through the unimpregnated GF textile (0|90). The mounting sequence was: release of one temporary flap, pulling and laminating of the GF-textile, and reattachment (tension force) of the temporary flap. This process was repeated to bond every final flap section in the manner of a back-step method with periods of resin hardening to ensure maintaining the correct pre-shape and the connection between the first membrane and the ring. To allow the second over-torsioned state for the bottom

membrane, the plate with the top membrane needed to be released from the jig arms (step 4). To avoid this single membrane taking all spring-back forces, the plate was partially restricted with tension straps. After that the last two flaps where the jig was mounted were bonded. The component was not flipped over but readjusted and mounted again to the jig, with torsioning the ring in opposite spin to achieve a second spring back effect for prestressing the second membrane later (step 5).

For installation of the second membrane, steps 3 and 4 were planned to be repeated, but the top membrane failed during prestressing the temporary flaps due to partially ripping of the laminated 0|90 fabric parallel to the rim edge. Through the piecewise mounting sequence relative forces parallel to the ring edge unfavorable for the used uncoated 0|90 GF-textile occurred. While during the analysis shear stresses and strains were checked, the installation introduced shear strains into the system. Using a soft coating that provides tear resistance would be a solution, but prevents us from laminating the GF onto the plate. The GF-textile was impregnated with resin and became stiff and brittle. To improve the construction, the textile fiber direction should be rotated, reinforced by a second layer, or impregnated with additional fibers with an 45° angle between the plate edge and membrane. To nevertheless achieve the planned bending-active tensile structure a cable net (consisting of 3 longitudinal and 5 transversal steel cables with 5 mm diameter) instead of the second membrane were mounted. This led to a different appearance as one side was not a closed surface any more, but was in terms of load-carrying action a comparable solution. With repetition of step 4 prestress to both sides of the ring was established and the structure of planned shape and targeted resistance could be achieved.

Figure 5: Overview pringle – top membrane construction process (step 1-5)

8. Results and Conclusion

A local bending-active tensile hybrid structure was designed, analyzed, fabricated and constructed; and demonstrated that a self-stressed-equilibrated system out of a continuous material can achieve a lightweight performative structural solution. Conventional constructions, which transfer the tensile forces of the membrane to the ground can lead to massive connections and support cables. This has an influence to the economical and visual quality of the structure. An integrated system as presented where the reaction forces are resolved within the system itself possesses potential to contribute to alternative solutions. The membrane showed a high prestress level, a secure membrane-plate connection and a stiffness gratifying serviceability demands, i.e. there was no visible deformation during a load test with a point load of 600 N (no horizontal constraint). The pringle finally was not integrated in the 'ITECH Research Demonstrator 2017-18' due to a plate failure of the primary structure, instead a non-structural replica was constructed and placed. As there is no post-stressing system available, e.g. turnbuckles, the system is relying on the ongoing spring back effect of the GFRP plate, and the creep of the membrane within this system should be further investigated.

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References

- [1] E. L.M. Slabbinck, S. Suzuki, J. J. Solly, A. Mader and J. Knippers, “Conceptual framework for analyzing and designing bending-active tensile hybrid structures,” in *Interfaces: architecture, engineering, science: Proceedings of the IASS Annual Symposium 2017*, Hamburg, Germany, September 25-28, 2017, A. Bögle and M. Grohmann Ed., 2017.
- [2] J. Lienhard and J. Knippers, “Bending-active textile hybrids,” in *Journal of the International Association for Shell and Spatial Structures (J. IASS)*, vol. 56 (2015), no. 1, pp. 37-48, March 2015
- [3] R. La Magna, “Bending-Active Plates. Strategies for the Induction of Curvature through the Means of Elastic Bending of Plate-based Structures,” *Stuttgart: Universität Stuttgart Inst. f. Tragkonstr. (Forschungsberichte aus dem Institut für Tragkonstruktionen und konstruktives Entwerfen der Universität Stuttgart, 43)*, 2017.
- [4] Lange+Ritter GmbH, “Verstärkt im Einsatz,” *Produktkatalog*, Gerlingen, 2019/2020.
- [5] P. D. Gosling, B. N. Bridgens, A. Albrecht, H. Alpermann, A. Angeleri, M. Barnes, N. Bartle, R. Canobbio, F. Dieringer, S. Gellin, W.J. Lewis, N. Mageau, R. Mahadevan, J-M. Marion, P. Marsden, E. Milligan, Y.P. Phang, K. Sahlin, B. Stimpfle, O. Suire and J. Uhlemann, “Analysis and design of membrane structures: Results of a round robin exercise,” in *Engineering Structures*, vol. 48, pp. 313-328, March 2013.
- [6] E. L.M. Slabbinck, A. Körner and J. Knippers, “Torsion as a design driver in plate-bending-active tensile structures,” in: *Proceedings of the IASS Annual Symposium (IASS)*, Hamburg, Germany, September 25-28, 2017.
- [7] SOFiSTiK AG ©, “ASE, General Static Analysis of Finite Element Structures,” *Sofistik manual Version 27.11*, pp. 2-68, Oberschleissheim, 2013.